

CHLORINATION OF BENZOIC ACID.

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When benzoic acid is chlorinated with hydrochloric acid and potassium chlorate two isomeric chloro-benzoic acids are obtained. These acids have been found to be 3 : 4-dichloro- and 2 : 5-dichlorobenzoic acids.

It was shown by three contemporary workers (Pfeifer, *Ber.*, 1871, 8, 658; *ibid.*, 1872, 8, 715; Beilstein, *Annalen*, 1875, 179, 291; Claus, *Ber.*, 1872, 8, 721) that benzoic acid on chlorination by potassium chlorate and hydrochloric acid gives two isomeric dichlorobenzoic acids. The methods adopted by these authors are practically the same. One part of benzoic acid was refluxed with 60 parts of 20% hydrochloric acid to which were slowly added 3 parts of potassium chlorate in concentrated solution. On evaporation of the reaction mixture, the two isomeric dichlorobenzoic acids were obtained as solid crystalline mass. The two acids were separated by fractional crystallisation of the total barium salts from water. The acid which was obtained from less soluble barium salt was called α -dichlorobenzoic acid and that obtained from more soluble barium salt was called β -dichlorobenzoic acid. These authors did not assign any position of the chlorine atoms in the two acids. Afterwards, Seelig (*Annalen*, 1886, 237, 129) in a review of dichloro toluenes and dichlorobenzoic acids described the α -acid as 2 : 3-dichlorobenzoic acid (I) and β -acid as 2 : 4-dichlorobenzoic acid (II).

(I)

(II)

(III)

(IV)

It has been conclusively proved by the present authors that the α -dichloro- and β -dichlorobenzoic acids obtained by chlorination of benzoic acid by potassium chlorate and hydrochloric acid by Pfeifer, Beilstein and Claus are 3 : 4- and 2 : 5-dichlorobenzoic acids respectively (III and IV).

The α -dichlorobenzoic acid has been found identical by mixed melting point with an authentic specimen of 3 : 4-dichlorobenzoic acid synthesised from 3 : 4-diaminotoluene by Sandmeyer's reaction and subsequent oxidation. The β -acid has similarly been identified with 2 : 5-dichlorobenzoic acid obtained from 2 : 5-diaminotoluene.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Chlorination of Benzoic Acid.—1200 C.c. of hydrochloric acid (20%) and 20 g. benzoic acid were heated in a flask on wiregauze and a concentrated aqueous solution of 60 g. potassium chlorate was added slowly within a course of 3 to 4 hours. Heating was then continued for several days. On evaporating off the reaction mixture on steam-bath a crystalline mass of a mixture of two dichlorobenzoic acids was obtained.

The crystalline mass was converted into barium salts by heating for 1 hour with excess of barium carbonate in about 200 c.c. of water. It was filtered while hot and the filtrate on cooling yielded crude barium salt of α -dichlorobenzoic acid. The mother liquor was evaporated on steam-bath to a small bulk and cooled when crude barium salt of β -dichlorobenzoic acid was obtained.

The crude barium salt of α -dichlorobenzoic acid was crystallised from water and decomposed

by dilute hydrochloric acid by warming. After cooling and filtering, *m*-dichlorobenzoic acid was obtained. This was purified by repeated crystallisation from benzene and was finally obtained as colourless needles, m.p. 208-9°. (Found : Cl, 36.92. Calc. for $C_7H_4O_2Cl_2$: Cl, 37.17 per cent). Mixed melting point of this product with an authentic specimen of 3 : 4-dichlorobenzoic acid was not depressed. The specimen was obtained in the following way. 3 : 4-Diaminotoluene after Sandmeyer's reaction with cuprous chloride in the usual way furnished 3 : 4-dichlorotoluene which was oxidised to 3 : 4-dichlorobenzoic acid by heating with concentrated nitric acid in a sealed tube.

The crude barium salt of β -dichlorobenzoic acid was crystallised from as little water as possible and was similarly decomposed as in the previous case. The β -dichlorobenzoic acid which was obtained was purified by repeated crystallisation from water, and was finally obtained as colourless needles, m.p. 154°. (Found : Cl, 36.89. Calc. for $C_7H_4O_2Cl_2$: Cl 37.17 percent). Mixed melting point of this product with an authentic specimen of 2 : 5-dichlorobenzoic acid was not depressed. The specimen of 2 : 5-dichlorobenzoic acid was obtained from 2 : 5-diaminotoluene by Sandmeyer's reaction and subsequent oxidation.

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